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SELF-ASSESSMENT OF COGNITIVE ACTIVITY OF MEDICAL STUDENTS IN THE DISCIPLINE OF 'PAEDIATRICS'

Abstract.

The article discusses the peculiarities of self-assessment of cognitive activity of medical students in the process of studying the discipline 'Paediatrics'. The role of self-assessment in the formation of professional competencies of future doctors is analysed, and factors influencing the adequacy of self-assessment, in particular psychological, pedagogical, organisational and content aspects, are identified. The importance of integrating modern teaching technologies, simulation techniques and clinical practices in the development of students' reflective skills is demonstrated. The need to create a supportive educational environment that encourages realistic assessment of one's own academic achievements is justified.

Keywords: *self-assessment, cognitive activity, medical students, paediatrics, professional competence, reflection.*

Introduction. Modern medical education is focused on training competent, responsible and reflective specialists who are capable of critical thinking, clinical analysis and continuous professional development. An important component of this process is the self-assessment of students' cognitive activity, which acts as a mechanism for internal control of learning, allowing them to adjust their own strategies and increase the effectiveness of professional knowledge acquisition. In the context of studying the discipline of 'Paediatrics', self-assessment is of particular importance, since paediatric practice involves responsible interaction with children, accuracy of diagnostic actions and a comprehensive understanding of age characteristics. For future doctors, the ability to adequately assess their own level of training is the basis for the formation of clinical competence and professional safety.

The aim of the work: to assess the characteristics of self-assessment of cognitive activity of medical students while studying the discipline 'Paediatrics' and to identify factors that ensure the formation of adequate self-assessment as a prerequisite for successful professional training.

Main part. Self-assessment of cognitive activity is an important component of the professional development of future doctors, as it determines the level of awareness of one's own knowledge, skills and abilities, forms the capacity for self-reflection and contributes to the development of clinical thinking. In the context of modern medical education, which is focused on a competency-based approach and requires students to actively search for, analyse and apply information, the issue of developing adequate self-assessment skills is

particularly relevant. The discipline of paediatrics occupies an important place in the system of professional training of doctors, as it covers a wide range of theoretical and practical knowledge about the health status of children of different age groups, the characteristics of the clinical course of diseases and the principles of care, prevention and treatment. The effectiveness of learning this discipline largely depends on how well students can objectively assess their own learning.

Self-assessment as a psychological and pedagogical phenomenon reflects a student's subjective attitude towards their level of preparation, success in completing educational tasks, and the effectiveness of applying the experience they've gained. Unlike external assessment, which is carried out by a teacher or standardised means of control, self-assessment covers the internal mechanisms of regulating learning activities. It is based on a combination of cognitive, motivational and emotional-volitional components that influence the quality of the learning process.

For medical students, whose studies are characterised by high intensity, complexity of material and significant responsibility for their future professional activities, the ability to adequately assess their own knowledge is a prerequisite for the formation of clinical competence and safe practice.

In the context of studying paediatrics, self-assessment of cognitive activity has a number of features related to the specifics of paediatric medicine. Firstly, a large amount of interdisciplinary knowledge integrating anatomical, physiological, biochemical, immunological, psycho-emotional and social aspects of childhood is important. Secondly, it is important to develop clinical observation skills, establish contact with young

patients and their parents, and assess age norms and developmental deviations. This places high demands on students' awareness of their own readiness to perform clinical actions, make decisions and analyse the results obtained.

Feedback from teachers is an important component in the formation of adequate self-esteem. Constructive assessment, focused not only on mistakes but also on students' strengths, helps to increase their academic confidence and motivation. The optimal approach is to use modern educational technologies, such as objective structured clinical examinations (OSCE), simulation training, and electronic platforms for self-assessment testing. These technologies make it possible to compare one's self-assessment with objective results and clarify one's actual level of preparation.

The nature of interaction within the student community also has a significant impact on the formation of self-assessment. Working in small groups, clinical case discussions, and peer assessment help students become aware of their own learning opportunities and develop communication and critical thinking skills. At the same time, the competitiveness that is often present in the medical environment can cause emotional stress and distort self-assessment, which requires teachers to pay attention to creating a supportive educational space.

Self-assessment of cognitive activity plays a key role in the professional development of future paediatricians. It influences students' ability to engage in continuous learning, which is a prerequisite for medical practice, and also contributes to the formation of a responsible attitude towards clinical decision-making.

Adequate self-assessment increases the level of self-organisation, promotes the development of autonomy in learning, and shapes readiness for professional challenges.

Conclusions. Self-assessment of cognitive activity is a key element in the professional development of future paediatricians. It acts as an internal regulator of learning, allowing students to critically reflect on their own achievements, identify the need for additional mastery of material, and develop a responsible attitude towards clinical practice. The formation of adequate self-assessment is possible under conditions of a comprehensive educational approach that combines high-quality pedagogical support, practice-oriented learning, modern assessment technologies, and a supportive psychological environment.

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